

THE CONSTITUTION IS THE BASIS FOR GUARANTEEING HUMAN RIGHTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17156899>

***Abstract.** It is confirmed by the example of the modern state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan that guarantees of human rights are one of the elements of the legal status of an individual. The content of constitutional guarantees of human rights is studied, the types of guarantees are analyzed, and a special classification of the types of constitutional guarantees of human rights is given. The measures for the development of human rights guarantees are considered. The definition of constitutional guarantees of human rights is presented. The article reveals the specifics of ensuring various types of constitutional rights and freedoms: personal, political, socio-economic. It is proved that the main purpose of constitutional guarantees is to force the state to fulfill its obligations in the sphere of realization of citizens' rights.*

***Keywords:** human rights, welfare state, guarantee of human rights, classification of human rights guarantees.*

Introduction. Guarantees of human rights are a necessary and important element of an individual's legal status. The system of ensuring human rights and freedoms is currently in the focus of legal and political reality, as human rights guarantees have become particularly important due to the consequences of the financial and economic crisis.

After achieving independence and establishing a new independent State, each nation and people defines its goals and prospects in the Constitution. After all, all existing constitutions in the world are closely linked to the political thinking, spirituality and culture of the people who created them.

In this sense, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan has also incorporated all the spiritual and cultural values, wisdom and moral qualities of our people, corresponding to its nature [1,2].

The reflection of the basic guarantees of human rights in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Basic Law is a policy document embodying the rights and freedoms of man and citizen, as well as their duties. The peculiarity of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is that it provides (in article 13) fully perfect and viable rights and freedoms that meet the requirements of the present and future of our country [1,2]. These "values": life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inalienable human rights are guaranteed (in article 109) personally by the head of the country and are aimed primarily at ensuring and protecting human rights and freedoms - "The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the guarantor of the observance of the rights and freedoms of citizens, the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan".

The Constitution [1,2] stipulates (in article 23) that the State, both on its territory and abroad, provides legal protection to its citizens. In the same place (in article 24), guarantees are provided for the protection of the rights and freedoms of foreign citizens and stateless persons on the territory of the republic in accordance with the norms of international law.

The state, relying on universal humanistic norms, ensures the necessary freedoms, rights and legitimate interests of its citizens [3], has created conditions for everyone to know their rights, to better understand the meaning and essence of the Constitution, its place and influence in the life of the people. For this:

- The Universal Declaration of Human Rights has been ratified and its humanistic norms have become the basic norms of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Ensuring the supremacy of the Constitution and its control over the constitutionality of normative legal acts adopted by the legislative and executive authorities is entrusted to the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The concept of constitutional guarantees of human rights. Constitutional guarantees of human rights are understood as a set of ways, conditions and means of ensuring human rights [4,5]. The importance of constitutional guarantees of human rights is very great, since in order for an individual to exercise his rights, these conditions and means must be enshrined in constitutional norms and secured by the force of the Constitution. The State and the system of bodies formed by it are responsible for ensuring human rights and freedoms.

It should be noted that if constitutional guarantees of political rights are provided without violations by state authorities and management, then for personal rights of citizens and guarantees of social rights are provided by obligations of state authorities. If necessary, the State must monitor their implementation.

In modern society, human rights guarantees, like the institution of human rights itself, are undergoing changes under the influence of political, social, economic and legal factors. During a certain period, the State, which influences the system of human rights guarantees, gives itself such powers as the protection of human rights, the maintenance of public order, the establishment of law and order, and justice. The main condition for the operation and effectiveness of these guarantees is their continuity and commitment [6,7].

The exercise of rights and freedoms is impossible without the existence of a reliable system of their guarantees. The State's responsibility in this area is a system of ways and means to ensure the guarantee of rights and freedoms. Real rights and freedoms have real security. Constitutional guarantees are an integral part of the constitutional status of an individual. Their absence makes it impossible to use legally established rights and freedoms.

The State is obliged to create material conditions for the realization of citizens' rights. For example, to ensure the right to free basic general education, the State must build schools, train teachers, publish textbooks, etc., since only in these conditions can the right to education be fully realized. Almost all modern constitutions contain a combination of the state's social obligations to citizens.

Achieving the ideas of a welfare state is a task that every highly developed and economically prosperous society sets itself [8].

Guarantees of human rights include both objective (the socio-economic structure of society, the state of the political system, etc.) and subjective (individual and mass legal awareness, the level of legal culture and its features) factors.

Objective guarantees. Objective guarantees create favorable conditions for the realization of human rights. These are economic, political, social, legal and ideological means, the action of which is aimed at maximizing the individual's ability to exercise his rights and freedoms. Among them, economic guarantees create a material base that allows for the full use of human rights and freedoms. They will ensure the economic stability of the country, the unity of the economic space,

the free movement of goods, services and finance, support for competition, and freedom of economic activity.

Organizational guarantees. This is the activity of government agencies that ensure the implementation and protection of human rights. This activity must meet two conditions: be legitimate and carried out by authorized state bodies, institutions and public organizations.

Based on these factors, in order to better understand the content of guarantees, it is advisable to classify them into objective, organizational and special types of human rights guarantees. In addition, it is necessary to keep in mind the availability of international, national, regional and local guarantees. Objective guarantees include the constitutional system of a particular country within which human rights are implemented.

Guarantees of the reality of rights and freedoms. The role of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan. A sign of democracy is the equality of all members of society before the law, ensuring the supremacy of the Constitution and laws. This is the most important sign of democracy.

The main purpose of constitutional guarantees is to force the state to fulfill its obligations in the field of the realization of citizens' rights, since the reality of rights and freedoms is manifested precisely through the reality of their guarantees [8].

The right to life is an inalienable right of every human being and is protected by law. This right was consolidated by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan through the abolition of the death penalty: the norm on the abolition of the death penalty was introduced into the Constitution and the honor and dignity of a person became inviolable, nothing can be a reason for their humiliation.

Constitutional guarantees are under the control of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It consists in the fact that, in accordance with the Constitution, it restrains and balances the legislative and executive bodies of state power. The limits of the competence of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan are defined by the law "On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan" (04/27/2021). It was adopted in order to increase the effectiveness and authority of the Constitutional Court, strengthen its independence, further democratize the procedure for its formation, and expand guarantees for the reliable protection of citizens' rights and freedoms.

Within the limits of his competence, he reviews and determines the compliance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan of laws and resolutions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees, decisions and orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In addition, it reviews and gives an opinion on the compliance of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan with all decisions of the government and local government authorities, international contractual and other obligations of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Determines the compliance of the constitutional laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan prior to their signing by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan also ratifies international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Clarifies the norms of the Constitution of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and their compliance with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Considers court appeals on compliance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan of normative legal acts to be applied in a particular case. The Constitutional Court also hears cases on complaints from

citizens and legal entities about violations of their constitutional rights and freedoms and other cases.

Annually submits information to the Chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the state of constitutional legality in the country based on the results of a generalization of the practice of constitutional legal proceedings.

The main importance of the existence of a democratic State lies in the full and consistent provision of citizens' rights. All types of government agencies, starting with the President, are involved in the mechanism of ensuring human rights. The President, as the head of State, is the guarantor of human rights and freedoms and ensures balanced activities of the authorities in ensuring them. The legislative bodies create the legal conditions for determining and protecting the legal possibilities of the individual at this stage of the historical development of the country. The Executive branch is obliged to strictly comply with all regulatory requirements for ensuring human rights and protection from violations. Regulatory authorities check the compliance of legal norms concerning human rights and freedoms with the actual situation. Judges protect human rights at all stages of their implementation, and apply State coercion measures against individuals and organizations that violate citizens' rights.

Conclusion. Using concrete examples of modern state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the article provides facts confirming that guarantees of human rights are one of the elements of the legal status of an individual.

To this end, the content of constitutional guarantees of human rights has been studied, the types and definitions of constitutional guarantees have been analyzed, and based on them, a special classification of types of constitutional guarantees of human rights has been given, as well as measures to develop guarantees of human rights.

In addition, the paper provides examples of ensuring various types of constitutional rights and freedoms: personal, political, socio-economic.

The main purpose of constitutional guarantees is formulated, which is to force the state to fulfill its obligations in the field of the realization of citizens' rights.

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